

MICROWAVE PROCESSING OF LARC-TPI POLYIMIDE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Polyimide composites have drawn great interest for their potential in aerospace applications. Polyimide processing methods are difficult and expensive. Microwave processing is an alternative method which may remove some of the difficulties encountered by conventional thermal methods. AS4/LARC-TPI composites were processed in an 18 cm (7 inch) 2.45 GHz resonant microwave cavity to compare materials processed by equivalent thermal cycles in ovens. Microwave processing was evaluated during the heating and processing of 24-ply unidirectional composites. Flexural testing was performed according to ASTM Standard D 790. Flexural tests revealed that the microwaved composites exhibited greater flexural strength and modulus than the thermal samples. A processing methodology was developed for the microwave method which shows great promise for future processing.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Polyimide; LARC-TPI; Microwave Processing; Flexural Testing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polyimide materials have exhibited great potential as a high-temperature matrix materials for composites. Their good mechanical properties and a high thermal resistance have been applied in the aerospace industry. LARC-TPI is a thermoplastic

resin developed by NASA with potential as a matrix material and an adhesive (1,2). LARC-TPI exhibits the high thermal properties typical of polyimides. The structure and chemistry of LARC-TPI is shown in Figure 1. Composite fabrication is usually facilitated by impregnating the fiber with the polyamic acid. The composite processing involves the conversion of the polyamic acid to the polyimide.

Polyimide materials applications have been limited by their difficult processing requirements (3). Often solvents and side products such as water or alcohol are evolved from the reaction of the intermediate forms of the polyimides. During reaction, an outer skin may form which traps the volatiles inside, creating voids. Long, extended curing cycles have been developed for polyimides which include the application of pressure to force the volatiles out and optimize mechanical properties. These processes are time intensive and must be carried out at high temperatures. Modified polyimides have also been developed to be processed by autoclave methods, but this is also an expensive and time-consuming method of processing.

Microwave processing has been developed as an alternative to conventional thermal processes. At Michigan State University, single-frequency resonant-mode microwave cavities have been developed for processing polymers and polymer composites (4,5,6). Microwave processing offers potential advantages over thermal processing. Heating is facilitated by the direct application of the microwave energy to the material. This manner of heating may lead to "inside-out" heating of the materials. Conventional heating methods heat from the outside surface in, which leads to the problem of void formation as the extent of reaction rises on the outside of the material faster than the inside. Mechanical properties have also been affected by the use of microwave methods (5).

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Hercules AS4 12 k graphite fiber was impregnated with LARC-TPI varnish obtained from Mitsui Toatsu Chemicals. The varnish was 28 % resin in its polyamic acid form in solution with diglyme.

The prepreg tape was cut into 7.6 cm squares and used for layup. The layups were placed in square teflon frames that acted as dams. Release film was placed over the top and the bottom of the sample and breather material was placed on top of the layup. A teflon square just under 7.6 cm in length was placed on top of the sample to be used as a piston. The sample was placed in a Carver press and pressed at 110 °C and 2.30 MPa for 10 minutes to consolidate the layup. This technique was used to compensate for the poor tack of the prepreg tape and a lack of pressure during processing. This method was referred to as prestaging.

The prestaged material was processed by microwave and thermal processes. The microwave samples were processed in an 18 cm cylindrical microwave cavity with a sliding short and an adjustable length operating at 2.45 GHz. The cavity and the equipment has been previously described in many other works (4,6). The sample was positioned after prestaging so that only vacuum bag and release film covered the composite. A round teflon plug with small holes drilled through it was placed on top of the composite. Quartz capillary tubes closed at one end were inserted through the holes to make contact with the composite and fluoroptic temperature probes were inserted into the tubes. A Luxtron 750 temperature sensing system was interfaced with a computer to record temperature profiles. Four temperature measurements were made on the surface of the composite. One probe was located in the center of the composite and the others were around its perimeter. A vacuum pump was also connected to the layup.

Microwave heating patterns were tested using an already reacted 24-ply composite. Different cavity modes were tested to find one which would heat the composite as uniformly as possible. The processing cycle chosen was a two-stage heating of the samples. The first stage was to heat under vacuum for 90 minutes at 60 Watts with the power cycled to maintain the temperature across the sample at approximately 180 °C. A second stage of heating was for 90 minutes at 80 Watts and maintained by power cycling at 250 °C. The second cycle was performed without vacuum.

Thermal samples were also prepared under vacuum. A programmable oven was set to heat the sample at 180 °C for a specified time. The sample was then heated in a programmable air-circulating oven for an hour at 250 °C. The programs that simulated the microwave cure were programmed to hold the sample for 1 hour at the specified times. The programming cycles were set with 30 minutes for heating the samples to temperature.

Mechanical testing was performed using a United Model SFM Testing System. The flexural tests were performed according to ASTM Standard D 790. For some of the samples, the thickness of the sample was too great to meet the required length-to-depth ratio, so the span was set to a fixed length for all samples.

The samples tested were a microwave composite produced by the aforementioned heating cycle with the fibers oriented at 45° with respect to the coupling probe in the microwave cavity. Another microwave sample was prepared with the orientation at 315° with respect to the coupling probe. Two thermal samples were also prepared in conventional ovens.

3. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The study of the heating modes of the 24-ply composite did not produce a single mode which heated the composite as evenly as desired. Figures 2 and 3 show the temperature profiles of two "failures". The thermal gradients were too large for use in processing. It was found, however, that the temperature profiles of the two modes were the inverse of one another. The same sample and probe positions were used for these heatings, but in one heating the temperature profile was $T_4 > T_1 > T_2 > T_3$ while the other was $T_3 > T_2 > T_1 > T_4$. This result led to an attempt to heat the sample with a mode-switching technique. The resulting heating pattern is presented in Figure 4. As can be seen, excellent temperature control was achieved. Uniform heating by mode-switching can be performed with two or more mode which form a uniformly-distributed electromagnetic field when superimposed upon one another (7).

This method of heating was used to process both microwave samples. Each sample had its own set of modes available for processing due to the different fiber orientations. The presence of the composite material disrupts the electromagnetic fields, and different heating patterns for the samples were produced. Figures 5 and 6 are the temperature profiles of the samples during the first heating stage in the microwave cavity. Figures 7 and 8 are the profiles of the second stage of heating at 250 °C. The composite heated with 315° orientation heated better for the first stage of heating, and the 45° orientation heated better for the second stage of the heating. One probe did not make good contact with the composite during the second stage heating of the 45°, so only three temperatures are shown in Figure 7.

Flexural testing results are presented in Table 1. The microwave samples exhibited higher flexural properties than the thermal samples. Due to the limited size of the coupons, the test did not meet ASTM standards. The results are only valid for comparison, but it can be seen that the microwave samples had stronger flexural properties.

TABLE 1
Results of Flexural Testing of
Thermal and Microwave Composites

Sample	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)
Thermal Sample	87.2 ± 8.2	17.3 ± 2.9
Thermal Sample	79.8 ± 10.6	12.1 ± 2.2
Microwave with 45° Fiber Orientation	104.4 ± 8.2	31.4 ± 5.9
Microwave with 315° Fiber Orientation	126.1 ± 8.0	27.6 ± 8.2

4. CONCLUSIONS

Polyimide composites were successfully processed in the microwave cavity. The AS4/LARC-TPI was heated during controlled cycles using the mode-switching technique. The mode-switching technique

offers good temperature control for the microwave processing. It also offers a potential for processing complex geometries in the future by microwave methods. The flexural properties of the microwave samples were higher for the samples processed by the microwave method. The sample oriented at 315° also exhibited a higher flexural strength than the other sample with the 45° orientation, but the 45° sample exhibited a higher flexural modulus. Further investigation of the mode-switching technique is needed to fully implement this into the methods of microwave processing.

5. REFERENCES

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FIGURE 1. Series of reactions forming LARC-TPI from starting materials.

FIGURE 2. The temperature profile of a processed 24-ply AS4/LARC-TPI composite heated at 315° orientation and cavity length of 11.35 cm.

Figure 3. Temperature profile of processed 24-ply AS4/LARC-TPI composite heated at 315° fiber orientation and cavity length of 13 cm.

FIGURE 4. The temperature profile of processed 24-ply AS4/LARC-TPI composite heated at 315° fiber orientation and by mode-switching techniques.

FIGURE 5. Temperature profile of the AS4/LARC-TPI composite Oriented at 315° during the first stage of microwave processing.

FIGURE 6. Temperature profile of the AS4/LARC-TPI composite oriented at 45° during the first stage of microwave processing.

FIGURE 7. Temperature profile of the AS4/LARC-TPI composite oriented at 315° during the second stage of microwave processing.

FIGURE 8. Temperature profile of the AS4/LARC-TPI composite oriented at 45° during the second stage of microwave processing.